

A persona-specific method to assess the FAIRness of data repositories

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Abstract

The FAIR Principles describe concepts for data repositories to make data more valuable to broader research communities. However, the principles can be interpreted and deployed in different ways and at different levels. This complicates the assessment of how well a repository meets the FAIR principles as one must bridge the gap between concepts and implementation choices given the constraints of the infrastructure of the repository and its overall goals. In this paper, we outline GO FAIR US's method for assessing the "FAIRness" of repositories which gathers information from repository team members knowledgeable about repository infrastructure, operations and services, and repository users based on typical roles or "personas." Our findings to date result from applying this methodology to repositories across the U.S. national health ecosystem. Our methodology adds to a growing literature of FAIR evaluation tools and methods, while building on this body of research in a way that others can replicate.

Keywords

Open science, FAIR Principles, FAIR Assessment

1. Introduction

The FAIR Principles are fifteen guiding principles for improving findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of digital resources. As they only provide guidance, they can be interpreted in very different and even inconsistent ways (Jacobsen et al., 2020). Indeed, there is growing literature field about tools for assessing the implementation of the FAIR Principles (Peters-von Gehlen et al., 2022; Kontsioti, 2023; Candela, Mangione and Pavone, 2024). Notwithstanding, the principles are valuable for the promotion of science research practices that

accelerate scientific discovery. This is why GO FAIR US has been commissioned to assess the extent to which repositories across various fields—including health (NIAID, 2024)—adhere to the FAIR Principles. This paper presents the method GO FAIR US has developed for this task, its basis in existing methodologies, and key considerations for its implementation.

1.1. Initial approach and challenges

Drawing on the literature on tools for assessing the “FAIRness” (the adherence to the FAIR Principles) of data repositories, GO FAIR US initially identified F-UJI as a candidate for the task at hand. F-UJI offers an automated approach to assessing a data object’s FAIRness (Devaraju, 2021).

Unfortunately, GO FAIR US learned of three limitations presented by different types of life science-focused repositories:

- **Password-Protected Repositories:** Since F-UJI assessments are done from a remote server, the tool can only scan websites where the data to be analyzed is publicly available. In other words, websites that keep data behind a password cannot be assessed.
- **Dynamically Generated Websites:** F-UJI does not have a JavaScript parser and cannot assess studies that lack a direct DOI or URL, but instead require a dynamic user interface to access the data. Meanwhile, some data repositories rely on JavaScript to create dynamically-generated UI elements to display information.
- **Studies vs Digital Objects:** F-UJI works well with repositories organized by files, each of which contains a study and is assigned a DOI. Some repositories, however, act more like databases, and F-UJI does not handle those repositories well. This final point warrants expanding.

The FAIR guidelines for assessing digital objects—such as individual database records—are still immature and therefore not addressed in the F-UJI tool. In fact, GO FAIR US found that a limitation of all automated FAIR assessment tools is that they are designed for specific data architectures. Many repositories don’t fit the one-file-per-DOI model, and thus no automated assessment tool can anticipate and adapt to every data architecture. Indeed, the primary or only data type in many repositories is an individual data file or a collection thereof, along with any associated reference files. In many repositories, a more complex set of data entities and structures are managed; for example, a collection of records about a specific entity type like “epitope” (Graybeal *et al.*, 2025) or a longitudinal dataset with many different observation types taken over many years. Currently, the FAIRness assessment tools available cannot fully account for this type of database. With this finding, GO FAIR US set out to develop a novel methodology for the assessment of diverse repositories. What has resulted is a more labor-intensive process with the advantage of providing much more granular insights to the various repositories GO FAIR US assesses, thus enabling more targeted and actionable implementation strategies.

1.2. Methodological assumptions

The methodology presented in the next section was developed on the premise that FAIR assessments should:

- Rely on metrics developed by the FAIR community while accounting for context- or domain-specific considerations;
- Strike a balance between working closely with repository staff to understand their practices, and minimizing disruption to their work; and
- Center on the goals, needs and services that repositories have, rather than impose rules.

Centering on the repository’s goals, needs and services is important. An assessment of the FAIRness of a

repository can be quite extensive and overwhelming, especially when assessing its approach to each of the 15 FAIR principles. The GO FAIR US team assumed that recommendations to improve the FAIRness of a repository would be more relevant and better received by the repository if they were strategically designed to focus on the motivations and set of incentives that drive the group being engaged. The team reasoned that, with a stakeholder-centered engagement, repositories could be motivated to:

- Increase reuse of their products (data, models, software);
- Increase interoperability of data within their repository and with other data sources; and
- Enable usage and impact assessment.

2. Methodology

The high-level outline of GO FAIR US’s approach to FAIR assessments is as follows:

1. Conduct desk-based research into the publicly available websites about the target repository’s FAIRness within its scientific domain;
2. Send key stakeholders a questionnaire on the data model, system structure, operations, services and uses of the target repository as they relate to each of the 15 FAIR principles;
3. Conduct follow-up interviews with the same stakeholders to clarify questionnaire responses, hold deeper discussions, and gain further insights;
4. Draft recommendations for FAIRification efforts (efforts that improve a repository’s FAIRness) that the target repository could take; and
5. Support repository leaders, as needed, by answering questions about the recommendations, discussing implementation choices, and ascertaining the most practicable strategies to take given the responses by the repository team to the preliminary recommendations.

2.1. Desk-based research and the profile template

The first stage of the methodology is designed to gain a general understanding of the target repository’s characteristics that are key to understanding where the repository fits in the broader, global FAIR landscape.

The characteristics chosen to describe the repositories are derived from information gathered by key FAIR registries, including fairsharing.org, re3data.org, data.gov, SciCrunch, an NIH registry of domain repositories (especially valuable where the target repository relates to health data), and GO FAIR US team members’ expertise grounded in their FAIR-related work and continuous engagement with the broader FAIR community. The characteristics are captured in a profile template. The repository’s profile template is populated by what can be ascertained from the registries’ information and various pages of the target repository’s public website. Characteristics included in the template describe the basic facts of the target repository (e.g., subject area coverage and length of operation). In addition, there are more FAIR-related factors such as standards used for

metadata schema and ontologies, data curation services, and certificates achieved (e.g., Core Trust Seal). See the supplementary material for the entire profile template.

The profile template provides a means for consistently assessing how each repository has approached FAIR implementation. The first iteration of a profile provides a FAIRness benchmark for the GO FAIR US team, and for the target repository itself. GO FAIR US considers these characteristics representative of some minimum standards that the repositories could meet in order to be included and indexed in the aforementioned registries. The initial profile is then fleshed out as more information becomes available during the entire assessment process.

2.2. Persona-specific questionnaires

The next stage involves gathering information from those working in or with the target repository. To do this, GO FAIR US developed a list of over eighty questions targeted at repository staff and stakeholders. The questions are mostly based on four sources and were then refined and supplemented by GO FAIR US team members. The four sources include:

- The European Research Data Landscape report that focused on gaining a better understanding of data production, consumption and deposition practices by researchers, and the responsiveness and readiness of research data repositories to implement the FAIR Principles (European Commission, 2022);
- A publication that resulted from FAIRsFAIR’s “Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe” program, which examines the alignment between the FAIR Data Principles with the CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Requirements, and considers how increased tiers of FAIRness and Trust can be described through capability or maturity levels (L’Hours et al., 2022);
- A set of recommendations from a Research Data Alliance Data Maturity Model Working Group (RDA, n.d.), which identifies FAIR data maturity model indicators, assessing each as either “essential,” “important,” or “useful” (Bahim et al., 2020); The GO FAIR US team then aligned the indicators with each of the FAIR principles; and
- Questions that EarthCube Office staff used to interview EarthCube project leads about the organization’s impact (Stocks and Evans, 2022).

The full questionnaire is quite comprehensive and unlikely to be answered in its entirety by any one repository stakeholder. To mitigate the impact on respondents’ day-to-day work, and target the questions to those most likely to have the expertise to respond, the questions are mapped across four personas:

1. A repository program officer or manager;
2. A member of the repository staff with technical or service responsibilities;
3. A researcher or other repository user who submits data to the repository; and
4. A researcher or other repository user who searches for and downloads data into the repository.

This list is not exhaustive; some personas may overlap. Generally, GO FAIR US has found that questions targeted to specific personas promise a comprehensive overview of a repository’s practices and stakeholders’ roles.

2.3. Follow-up interviews

The third stage is to conduct follow-up interviews. The goals here are to (i) get a deeper understanding of key technical aspects of practice and implementation approaches related to each of the FAIR Principles, (ii) identify and discuss repository needs and issues within a repository that may prevent implementing the Principles, and

(iii) translate those needs and possible solutions into relevant FAIR-implementation recommendations from which the repository leadership may choose to pursue.

The interview questions themselves help:

1. Verify or expand upon answers that had been previously provided through the questionnaire or that had been discovered in the repository profile;
2. Identify how the individuals or the repository support researchers in making their data FAIR; and
3. Identify whether the repository would like additional information or assistance in making the repository data or services more FAIR.

2.4. Analysis and recommendations

With data gathered throughout each stage, a final analysis is conducted before drafting recommendations. The final analysis helps bridge gaps between the practices repository stakeholders currently employ and feasible interventions that would enable the repository both to engage with the wider data ecosystem and to facilitate more sharing and reuse of their data.

Regarding technical standards, the GO FAIR US team has found that practices can be easily evaluated for their adoption of explicit specifications designed to increase interoperability, i.e., both syntactic and semantic specifications. Typically, greater adoption of—and adherence to— well-defined specifications leads to improved interoperability. The metadata resources themselves are assessed according to their use of persistent identifiers, controlled vocabularies and structured formats to enhance FAIR properties.

In particular, evaluating web architecture involves the inspection of structural metadata for the target repository's web pages when available or derivable, e.g., sitemaps and API endpoints that make both structural metadata and scientific data available in FAIR-friendly formats. For example, if metadata attributes are defined for a repository web page that follows schema.org specifications (especially those of key entities such as study or dataset pages), the values for those attributes can be generated in JSON-LD and published. This would facilitate discovery and access to those pages. In addition, GO FAIR US examines whether a repository's operational practices can be compared to best architectural practices (such as those related to a repository's web presence), though this evaluation requires greater technical sophistication, can be more subjective, and has not been readily understood by repository technical teams.

Combined, GO FAIR US assesses architectural, data model, and metadata model approaches for the repository's alignment to FAIR for their resultant capability to interoperate with both relevant discovery portals such as data.gov or SciCrunch, and potential third-party indexes, such as Google Dataset Search (Google, n.d.). The aggregated analyses and recommendations provide an overall view of the data landscape in which a repository operates, and inform strategic directions that could be employed by key players to bring entire data ecosystems toward integrated FAIRness.

2.5. Implementation

Although offering recommendations may mark the end of the FAIR assessment process, a great deal more is to be done for a target repository's FAIRification. While GO FAIR US has discovered that evaluators and target repositories can learn a lot together through the preceding four stages, recommendations may still require clarification. Indeed, the GO FAIR US team has continued to partner with the assessed repositories to offer clarification on the recommendations as well as guidance on making the most practicable implementation choices.

3. Challenges and insights

Implementing the above methodology for FAIR assessment of various repositories has uncovered certain challenges that should be considered.

3.1. Establish a common understanding of FAIR-related concepts

It is crucial to establish a common understanding of various concepts, most notably of a target repository's use of what constitutes "metadata" and "data."

Clear definitions become especially important when analyzing responses gathered through questionnaires and interviews. Indeed, repository teams often considered "metadata" to be what GO FAIR US came to call the "scientific" metadata, whereas many of the questions the GO FAIR US team asks pertain to "FAIR" metadata. On the one hand, scientific metadata came to be considered as descriptors of the scientific content in datasets or tool outputs, such as the names of diseases or drugs that might appear in a repository's data dictionary along with its list of values. By contrast, FAIR metadata refers to information about the repository's assets and services — such as key entity types, provenance (e.g., date/time dataset received, version)— and other contextual information that would be useful for others to know when contemplating the use/reuse of the repository and its assets.

3.2. Get repository staff and user buy-in but test assumptions

Plan to work closely with a variety of the target repository's team members and users from the onset, as both parties must see the value of the assessment process. This helps stakeholders better understand the importance of FAIRness assessment efforts despite the disruption to their daily work.

One of the goals of GO FAIR US for the landscaping project is to get as widespread a range of views as possible about what target repositories are doing to implement the FAIR principles. With respect to repository staff, repository leadership may want to protect staff members' time (which is understandable). Regarding repository users, GO FAIR US seeks to canvas researchers to uncover information related to change management and other social factors, and to collect ideas for improvement that could help implement FAIR practices more effectively.

Furthermore, there is a need to be open-minded about potential findings, as certain assumptions may not hold. In one instance, the GO FAIR US team assumed that repository "owners" are less technically knowledgeable than technical and service staff. This turned out to be incorrect in some cases. The gradual roll-out of the assessment methodology allowed the team to discover the varied ways that roles and expertise are distributed across each repository. With this understanding, alternative approaches going forward may include asking all questions of every respondent, making the questionnaires more adaptive using conditional logic or refining the personas used to characterize respondents.

3.3. Anticipate diverse implementations but gather information consistently

When designing information collection, plan for the widest possible range of repository needs and implementation choices while maintaining consistency in approach.

The FAIRness assessment was originally designed to be conducted across a number of different repositories within the health data ecosystem, but needed to be consistent in approach. A balance had to be struck between providing customized recommendations for each repository, and informing possible ecosystem-wide strategic choices by extrapolating from the individual repository recommendations. This raised a unique challenge for GO FAIR US. To ensure the recommendations were comparable, it was paramount that underlying evidence

generated from the profiles, questionnaires, interviews, and analyses be generated and presented in a consistent format. To meet this need, the GO FAIR US team identified major facets that can impact FAIRness evaluations within the ecosystem. These facets seem to offer the best approaches to improve the repositories' FAIRness and interoperability. More information about these major facets is presently out of scope but will be described more completely in subsequent papers.

By using the major facets consistently, it is possible to note when, how, and why a repository makes choices that affect its overall FAIRness, consequently making it more difficult to conduct a comprehensive FAIR assessment. For example, specializations around particular domains or scientific objectives can potentially limit a FAIR evaluation. If a repository stores some sensitive data or metadata, making that information FAIR could violate the repository's mission, and any FAIR analyses or metrics should reflect that reality. Consider also a repository storing data to provide a discovery or analytic service rather than research products; how would a FAIR evaluation provide insight into the repository's value to its users?¹

To address these and other questions that will undoubtedly arise, the GO FAIR US team has developed several rubrics —similar to the repository facets mentioned above— that are evaluated for their usefulness in other FAIR assessment processes. One of these rubrics concerns the appropriate way to evaluate repositories built to describe real-world entities (e.g., epitopes, genes, or proteins), rather than studies or datasets.

4. Conclusion

This paper presents a persona-specific methodology for FAIR assessments. Unlike many other methods, this approach relies primarily on human expertise and engagement with repository staff. In other words, the presented methodology does not intend to automate FAIR assessments; indeed, it aims to overcome the limitations of technologically driven approaches. Furthermore, the presented methodology has been tested with various repositories within the health data ecosystem and will, undoubtedly, continue to be improved with each implementation.

Through the development and deployment of the persona-specific methodology, GO FAIR US has discovered needed improvements: the need for repository staff buy-in, testing one's assumptions, and balancing consistent data-generation approaches with adaptable implementation methods in light of repositories' circumstances.

¹ Example: A web search engine offers transitory responses to search queries, but insufficient mechanisms to persistently identify and/or reuse a search query. The products of these services and the services themselves are rarely cited except to demonstrate completeness of search, and are heavily evaluated on their speed, ease of use, and relevance of results. Would it still be valuable to rate them on FAIRness criteria (probably rating very low) when their perceived importance to users is more focused on the immediate functional value of the service?

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Supplementary Material

Appendix: Data Repository Template

Initials of GO FAIR US team completing this form:

Repository Name:

Repository URL:

Main Physical location(s):

Description

Abstract	
Stakeholders/audience	
Founded by	
Duration of service	
Date of entry into NIH	
Approximate number of datasets or records	
Sensitivities (e.g., HIPAA?)	

Institution Name of Organization Funding Repo (full):

Institution acronym for above:

Institution Name of organization managing repo (full):

Institution acronym for above:

Registries (contributing to)

Registry Name	Registry ID	Registry Type (per CV for Registry from fairsharing.org)	Registry Record Documentation URL
re3data			

Registry Name	Registry ID	Registry Type (per CV for Registry from fairsharing.org))	Registry Record Documentation URL
fairsharing			
data.gov			
NIH Collections	Access via https://fairsharing.org/3493 ; no registry IDs		
SciCrunch			

Certificates achieved, e.g., Core Trust Seal:

Certificate Name

Certificate Start Date

Certificate End Date

Certificate URL

Repository Characteristics:

Repo Properties

(CV from fairsharing.org: Open data submission; Open timeframe for data deposit; NIH funding support; Sustained support; All)

Property Name	Check if applicable
Open data submission	
Open timeframe for data deposit	
NIH funding support	
Sustained support	

All	
-----	--

Repo Model System

(CV from NIH Collections web page: human; non-human; all)

Model System	Check if applicable
human	
non-human	

Subject area(s)

(CV from NIH Collections web page: Clinical research; Imaging; Neuroscience; Computational biology; Other; Sequence biology; Behavioral and social sciences; All)

Subject Area	Check if applicable
Clinical research	
Imaging	
Neuroscience	
Computational biology	
Sequence biology	
Behavioral and social sciences	
Other	
All	

FAIR support services offered

(CV from fairsharing.org: Search & Download; Browse Publications; Shared Data; Cell Ontology Browser; Submit; Batch Update; Upload Data). The process categories include Access Method, Example URL, Documentation URL

with designation of Read and Write

Repo Process Name	Check if applicable	Text if needed
Search & Download		
Browse Publications		
Shared Data		
Cell Ontology Browser		
Submit		
Batch Update		
Upload Data		
Access Method		
Example URL		
Documentation URL (Read)		
Documentation (Write)		

Data Curation/Stewardship Characteristics

Characteristic	Check if applicable with X; blank if No; U if unable to determine;	Notes
Citation and Availability Statement displayed on page where data can be accessed		
Supplemental material for Availability Statement present/linked including documentation, license, access		

Characteristic	Check if applicable with X; blank if No; U if unable to determine;	Notes
conditions, agreements, contact information, software tools.		
Journal Availability Statement template can be provided		
Data usage statistics (or information on how to access statistics) present on data page		
GREI repositories display usage statistics for tracking/reporting purposes		
Persistent identifier/link to repository submission and workflow status/decision		
Responds to challenge of authors needing to include a persistent identifier/link at time of journal publication		
Information/statement displayed about persistence of metadata/data if not leveraging common identifiers/community norms		
Governance/sustainability information to assess long term sustainability		
Controlled vocabularies are documented & where		
Open formats for data are accepted and used		

Characteristic	Check if applicable with X; blank if No; U if unable to determine;	Notes
Provenance information (data collection and generation) captured in data download (e.g., header)		
Preservation policy statement exists and where		
Database search/filter parameters available; where		
Help Documentation exists and where		

Procedures for access (for whom)	
Requirements for deposit	
Usage policies	
Usage policy name	
Usage policy URL	
Licenses	
Repo Access type	
Repo Access restriction	
Repo Access license name	
Repo Access license URL	
Data Access type	
Data Access restriction	
Data Access license name	
Data Access license URL	
Data Upload type	
Data Upload restriction	
Data Upload license name	
Data Upload license URL	
API type	

API URL	
API Documentation link	

Standards

Metadata description name	
Metadata standard URL	
Research Data PID System(s)	

Citations

Citation Reference System	
Citation Reference Guidance Link	
Preferred or Example Citation	

Related Standards (e.g., Publication)

Research Data Usage Metrics

Associated Tools

Data Formats (e.g., use of e-notebooks?)

Software used (for what?)

Key Contacts (name and responsibility)

(Suggested roles = Program mgr., PI, Repository mgr., Data steward or curator; repository / software development manager)

References for background information and seminal publications for the data

Additional Notes:

Community gathering events (Conference names, frequency of cyclical events, target audiences for events)	
Miscellaneous	

